

An Explainable Machine Learning Framework for Mobile Banking Fraud Prediction

Mohammed Jieaf¹, Jawad Al Mujahid², Mohaiminul Kabir¹, Sakib Rahman¹, Ekramul Hasib¹, Md.Mortuza Ahmmed³

¹Department of Computer Science, American International University Bangladesh

²Department of Computer Science, International Islamic University Chittagong

³Department of Mathematics, American International University Bangladesh

Abstract— The increase in the number of digital financial transactions brings many challenges in the form of mobile banking fraud. In this manuscript, we propose a machine learning approach for the prediction of such frauds from transaction data. The data preprocessing techniques used were missing value imputation and SMOTE oversampling. The gradient boosting model was able to achieve the highest accuracy (95.50) and AUC (97.89). Furthermore, the Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) analysis with ELI5 identified important features related to fraud such as amount, oldbalanceOrg, and newbalanceOrig leading to better model interpretability.

Keywords— Mobile Banking Fraud, Machine Learning, Gradient Boosting, Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)

I. Introduction

The increasing use of digital financial transactions and the growing risk of fraudulent activities have made mobile banking fraud a major concern. The early detection of fraudulent transactions is very important for secure and reliable mobile banking service. In this paper, a machine learning based mobile banking fraud detection model is proposed based on transaction data. Furthermore, the most relevant features related to fraud were detected by means of explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) methods, and the interpretability of the predictive model was improved.

II. Methodology

The study used a machine learning approach to prediction Mobile Banking Fraud. The dataset was originally downloaded from Kaggle, for Mobile Banking Fraud.

Pre-processing: The following procedures were used to treat missing values for data preprocessing: Missing numeric values were replaced with median and missing categorical values with mode. No duplicates were found. The outliers were capped to reduce their effect on the model performance.

Model Evaluation: The pre-processed data were then divided into a training and testing set. The SMOTE approach was used to handle the class imbalance in target variable. Various machine learning algorithms were experimented with and developed for the prediction of ischemic heart disease. Reliability of the model was tested on accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, AUC and K-Fold Cross Validation.

Explainable AI(XAI): We used Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) tools, especially ELI5, to understand the model and discover the most important features that predict mobile banking fraud.

III. Results and Discussion

This Table 1 presents **Gradient Boosting (GB)** classifier shows highest performance than the other models in the prediction Mobile Banking Fraud, with an accuracy of **95.50%**, precision of **95.51%**, recall of **95.50%**, F1-score of **95.50%** and AUC of **97.89%**. The performance of **Random Forest(RF)**, **Extra Tree**

Table 1. Performance Comparison of ML Models

Model	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.	F1	AUC
GB	95.50	95.51	95.50	95.50	97.89
RF	94.10	94.34	94.23	94.21	96.67
ET	93.53	93.51	93.52	93.51	94.78
AdaBoost	92.01	92.03	92.56	92.34	93.53

(ET) and AdaBoost(AB) was comparatively lower.

Figure 1. Confusion Matrix

The **Gradient Boosting** model did a good job at classifying mobile banking fraud incidents. Although some misclassifications occurred, the true negative and true positive prediction values were high.

IV. Conclusion

The study demonstrated the potential of machine learning methods for **fraud detection in mobile banking**. The **Gradient Boosting** classifier was the best performing model in terms of predictive performance. Also, **ELI5** feature importance analysis showed that the most important features were **amount**, **oldbalanceOrg**, **newbalanceOrig**, **oldbalanceDest**, and **step**, and transaction types like **type_TRANSFER** and **type_CASH_OUT** were also important in fraud detection. The proposed method can be potential to secure the decision making and to enhance the fraud prevention in mobile banking systems.

References

- [1] M. H. Anne, "AI-powered fraud detection in mobile banking applications: Leveraging machine learning for enhanced security," *Journal of Computer Science and Technology Studies*, vol. 7, no. 11, pp. 09–14, 2025.